

SOCIOECONOMIC AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

Production

Production potential and economics of rice-based relay cropping systems

S. S. Patra and T. Barik, Regional Research Station (RRS), Keonjhar, Orissa 758002; and A. Misra, Agronomy Department, College of Agriculture, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Bhubaneswar, Orissa, India

We experimented 1985-86 and 1986-87 with eight relay cropping systems—rice - field pea, rice - bengal gram, rice - lentil, rice - lathyrus, rice - green gram, rice - black gram, rice - linseed, and rice - coriander—in the rainfed lowlands at RRS, Keonjhar. Relay crops were broadcast in soft mud at 1.5 times normal seeding rates, 19 Nov 1985 and

Production and economics of different rice-based relay cropping systems.^a 1985-87, Orissa, India.

Cropping system	Rice grain yield (t/ha)	Rice straw yield (t/ha)	Relay crop green pod or grain yield ^b (t/ha)	Gross profit (\$/ha)	Net profit (\$/ha)
Rice - field pea	5.2	4.1	2.9	1191.31	891.61
Rice - Bengal gram	4.8	3.9	8.0+	944.38	686.72
Rice - lentil	4.7	3.7	0.4	791.02	525.99
Rice - lathyrus	4.6	3.6	0.5	784.45	529.85
Rice - linseed	4.5	3.5	0.3	688.98	451.09
Rice - coriander	4.4	3.5	0.2	756.72	506.06
Rice - green gram	4.4	3.4	F	592.04	365.99
Rice - black gram	4.5	3.5	F	604.60	378.32

^aMean of 2 yr. ^bF = failed. + = green pod.

31 Oct 1986, 15-20 d before rice harvest (dough stage). The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications.

Local improved rice variety T141 (145 d) was transplanted both years. Soil of the experimental site was clay loam, of medium fertility, with pH 6.5.

Rice - field pea was most economic, with a \$891.61/ha net profit (the field pea in this system was sold as a green pod vegetable) (see table). Two crops—green gram and black gram—failed both years because of shading, excessive initial soil moisture, and low temperature. □

Economics of N application to rice in rainfed lowland

S. K. Gupta, Indian Council of Agricultural Research Complex for N.E.H. Region, Tripura Centre, Lembucherra 799210, India

Field trials were conducted during dry season 1981 and 1982 to evaluate the economics of N application to rice. Tripura is situated between 22°56' and 24°32' N, 90°10' and 92°21' E. The climate is generally warm and humid, with temperatures ranging from 9 to 34 °C. Average annual rainfall is 2,100 mm. Soil is sandy loam, with pH 5.4, 0.06% total N, and 0.9% organic C.

Four levels of N (0, 40, 80, and 120 kg/ha) were applied in randomized block design, replicated three times. A uniform 17.6 kg P and 33 kg K/ha were applied as single superphosphate and muriate of potash. Two seedlings of 28-

Table 1. Rice yield under different N levels. Tripura, India, 1981 and 1982 dry season.

N level (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)		
	1981	1982	Mean
Control	1.6	2.0	1.8
40	2.6	2.5	2.6
80	3.0	2.8	2.9
120	2.0	2.6	2.3
SE ±	0.3	0.3	0.3
LSD (0.05)	0.6	0.1	0.6

d-old IR36 were transplanted the second week of Feb both years. Recommended agronomic practices were followed.

N at 80 kg/ha yielded significantly higher both years (Table 1).

Response curves were fitted for individual years (see figure). The equations fit the data, as evidenced by significant coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.95 - 0.99$) and quadratic effects

Effect of N fertilization on grain yield of dry season rice IR36 on lunga land in Tripura, India.

(SE ± 0.32, 0.43), indicating that higher N would depress yield.

Expected yield for N level and the N level predicted to give the highest and